

Business Opportunities for Small Business Entrepreneurs in India

N. Madhumithaa

Research Scholar – MBA

Hindustan University

Padur, Kelambakam, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Dr. M.K. Badri Narayanan

Associate Professor - MBA

Hindustan University, Kelambakam, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Abstract

In a developing country like India, Small Scale Entrepreneurship plays a significant role in economic development of the country. These industries, by and large represent a stage in economic transition from traditional to modern technology after globalization. The variation in transitional nature of this process is reflected in the diversity of these industries. Most of the small scale industries use simple skills and machinery. Besides playing economic role in the country, small scale industries, because of their unique economic and organizational characteristics, also play social and political role in local employment creation, balanced resource utilization, income generation and in helping to promote change in a gradual and peaceful manner.

The study of entrepreneurship is essential not only to solve the problem of industrial development but also to solve the problems of unemployment, unbalanced areas development, concentration of economic power and diversion of profits from traditional avenues of investment. In this backdrop, the present study attempts to get insights to the various business opportunities for small scale entrepreneurs, the definition of small scale enterprises and also to study the small scale entrepreneurship in India.

Key Word: *Small Scale Business, Opportunities, Evolution, Challenges*

I. INTRODUCTION

(a) Meaning of Entrepreneurship

An entrepreneur is a person who operates a new venture and also inherits some risks and is able to look at the environment, The great ones are ready to be laughed at and criticized in the beginning because they can see their path ahead and are too busy working towards their dream, True entrepreneurs are resourceful, passionate and driven to succeed and improve.

The term “entrepreneurship” comes from the French verb “entreprendre” and the German word “unternehmen”, both means to “undertake”. By grave and Hofer in 1891 defined the entrepreneurial process as , involving all the functions, activities, and actions associated with perceiving of opportunities and creation of organizations to pursue them.

(b) Significance of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurs play an important role in developing and contributing to the economy of a nation. It is all the more in a developing world where are ample opportunities for innovations to exploit the available resources and initiate entrepreneurial ventures.

Entrepreneurship has gained greater significance at global level under changing economic scenario. Global economy in general and Indian economy in particular is poised for accelerated growth driven by entrepreneurship. Admits environment of super mall culture we find plenty of scope for entrepreneurship in trading and manufacturing.

Entrepreneurship as a stabilizing force limits entrepreneurship to reading markets disequilibria, while entrepreneurship defined as owning and operating a business, denies the possibility of entrepreneurial behavior by non-owners, employees and managers who have no equity stake in the business. Therefore, the most appropriate definition of entrepreneurship that would fit into the rural development context, argued here, is the broader one, the one which defines entrepreneurship as: "a force that mobilizes other resources to meet unmet market demand", "the ability to create and build something from practically nothing", "the process of creating value by pulling together a unique package of resources to exploit an opportunity".

The entrepreneurship is a very old concept according to which anyone who runs business is called an entrepreneur. The more precise meaning of entrepreneur is; one who perceives a need and then brings together manpower, material and capital required to meet that need. Entrepreneur is one who understands the market dynamics and searches for change respond to it and exploit it as an opportunity.

(c) The Nature of Entrepreneurship

In recent years the subject of entrepreneurship has become quite popular, though very few people thoroughly understand the concept. Most researchers agree that the term refers to entrepreneurial activities that receive organizational sanction and resource commitments for the purpose of innovative results. The major thrust in present scenario is to develop small scale entrepreneurship in India with a view to increase employment opportunities with increasing percentage of youth population.

II. METHODOLOGICAL VIEW OF STUDY

In the light of above mentioned literature, the present study attempts to get insights to review, in brief, the opportunities available for small entrepreneurs, the definition of small scale enterprise and also to study development of the small scale entrepreneurship in India. The study is based on the secondary data made available by the offices –Director of Industries and District Industries Centres, various publications of Government of India such as Census of Small Scale Industries, Economic Survey and report on Small Enterprises.

III. CURRENT SCENARIO OF SMALL SCALE ENTERPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

Definition of Small Scale Entrepreneurship: To appreciate small scale entrepreneurship in India, a basic understanding of the definition and scope of the terminology “small enterprise” is very necessary. The definition of a small enterprise varies across countries, industries, agencies and authors. The terminology “small enterprise” itself is used by different countries by different nomenclatures such as small business, small firm and small industries and so on. Throughout this study the terms small enterprise, small firm and small business are used interchangeably. Vepa (1988) has listed the various terminologies used in some countries which are depicted in Table 1. Atkins and Lowe (1997) noted that as many as 40 different definitions of small firms have been reported in the literature, and generally there appears to be very little consistency in criteria used to define small enterprises. The criteria are

many, such as number of employees, annual sales revenue, value of fixed assets/plant and machinery and the management structure.

Table 1: Terminologies and scope of Small Industry in select countries

S.No	Country	Terminology	Scope
1	Japan	Small enterprise	Manufacturing, mining, Services, trading (wholesale and retail)
2	India	Small Industry/enterprise/ business	Manufacturing, repair and services
3	Korea	Small enterprise	Manufacturing, mines, construction, commerce
4	USA / Canada	Small Business	Manufacturing, Services, trading
5	UK	Small firms	Manufacturing, commerce (both retail and wholesale), construction, mining, transport

In India, the small industry is defined in terms of investment ceiling. Also the small industry sector enjoys a special reservation policy in terms of items of manufacture. The investment limit ceiling was revised by the central government from time to time, depending on the industrial and economic development and needs of entrepreneurs.

Initially, there was an additional condition limiting number of persons employed, the same was deleted in 1960. Further, the investment ceiling was linked to plant and machinery only, excluding investment in other fixed assets i.e., land and building. The reason was to define small industry with respect to such investments mainly in productive assets. The investment limit was raised to Rs. 30 million based on the recommendations of the Report of the Expert Committee on Small Enterprises, with Dr. Abid Hossain as Chairman. The report, submitted to the Central Government in July 1997, recommended that the definition of small scale industries be broadened to small scale enterprises and allowing incentives, credit facilities, and promotional facilities to flow to all small enterprises. On line with this, it was recommended that the investment limit of small scale enterprise be raised to Rs. 30 million. But later, it was felt that this raise in investment limit up to Rs. 30 million did not truly result in accelerated investments in small enterprises. Large majority of small enterprises still belong to the lower investments up to Rs. 1 million.

Evolution of Small Scale enterprise/ Business: The evolution of the Indian entrepreneurship can be traced back to even as early as Rigveda, when metal handicrafts existed in the society (Rao, 1969). This would bring the point home that handicrafts entrepreneurship in India was as old as the human civilization itself and was nurtured by the

craftsmen as a part of their duty towards the society. Before India came into contact with the west, people were organized in a particular type of economic and social system of the village community. Contributing factors to the absence of localization of industry in ancient India (Deshpande, 1984) organized industrial activity was observable among the Indian artisans in a few recognizable products in the cities of Banaras, Allahabad, Gaya, Puri and Mirzapur which were established on their river basins as a means of transportation facilities. Bengal enjoyed worldwide celebrity for corah, Lucknow forchintzes, Ahmedabad for dupattas and dhotis, Nagpur for silk-bordered clothes, Kashmir for shawls and Banaras for metal wares. Thus till the earlier years of the eighteenth century, India enjoyed the prestigious status of the queen of the International trade with the help of its handicrafts.

The emergence of manufacturing entrepreneurship can be noticed in the second half of the nineteenth century. Ranchodlal chotalal, a Nagar Brahman, was the first Indian to think of setting up the textile manufacturing on the modern factory lines in 1847. Probably the major Indian contribution in the Nineteenth century came in the field of banking, where every important company owned its existence, in part, to the enterprise and capital of Indians (Rungta, 1970). A few beginnings were made by Indians in heavy industries—steel, engineering, electric power and shipping (Lamb, 1955) in the early part of the twentieth century. The second wave of entrepreneurship growth in India began after the First World War.

Current Scenario: The government gave mild protection and some encouragement to the select forms of enterprise but the development that took place did not bring about either a degree of regional balance or major structural changes in the Indian economy. Thus there was a significant growth of small scale enterprise population, their production and employment, besides contributing to a major share of country's exports.

Table 2 Production, Employment and Exports in Small Scale Sectors in India

Year	Production (Rs million)	Employment (Rs million)	Exports (Rs million)	Growth rate of production	Growth rate of exports
2002-03	30,67,710	26.02	8601.3	8.68	20.73
2003-04	33,63,440	27.14	9764.4	9.64	13.52
2004-05	37,29,380	28.26	12,441.70	10.38	27.42
2005-06	41,88,840	29.49	15,024.20	12.32	20.75
2006-07	47,16,630	31.26	18,253.80	12.59	21.49
2007-08	53,29,790	32.23	20,201.70	12.99	10.67
2008-09	59,42,950	33.44	21,438.70	11.5	6.12
2009-10	65,56,110	35.24	23,875.20	10.32	11.36
2010-11	72,33,190	37.85	25,683.40	10.33	7.57
2011-12	80,45,130	40.96	28,384.70	11.22	10.52

The small industry is being perceived as vital sub-sector of the economy. Small industry generates large employment, removes regional imbalance by contributing to the economic development.

IV Business Opportunities for Small Business Entrepreneurs

1. **Tourism:** Tourism has emerged as number one largest smokeless and fast growing industry in the world due to its ample promises and prospects. Presently, it accounts for 8% of the world trade and around 20 % of service sector in the world.

Evidences indicate that many countries have progressed from backward to developing to developed, mainly due to tourism development. For example, tourism industry contributes to more than 70% of the national income of some of the countries like Malaysia and Singapore. However, its share to the national income of India is still dismally low at 2.5% because it's an unorganized sector; India lacks trained professionals in the tourism and hospitality sectors. Any business in this sector will thrive in the long run as the demand continues to grow every year. Recognizing the India's vast tourism potential, the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) has predicted "India has potential to become number one tourist destination in the world with the demand growing at 10.1% per annum."

Successful Indian Innovative Travel and Tourism startups

Name	Founder	Year	Business
Cleartrip	Hrush Bhatt	2006	Indian online Travel
Zomato	Deepinder Goyal	2008	online restrant discovery guide
DigiValet	Rahul Salgia	2008	Hotel Logistics Software
Girls on the Go Club	Piya Bose	2008	Travel arrangements exclusively for womens
Thrillophilia	Chitra Gurnani Daga	2008	Travellers unique Experience
White Collar Hippie	White Collar Hippie	2008	Organic Travel
Gautam Shewakramani	AudioCompass	2008	Travel app for stories of destination

2. **Automobile:** India has made much headway in industry and by now has emerges as a hot spot for automobiles and auto-components. A cost- effective hub for auto components sourcing for global auto makers, the automobile sector is by all indications a potential sector for entrepreneurs in India.

This is confirmed by a record increase registered by automobile industry in India. The automobile industry recorded a 26 per cent growth in domestic sales in the year 2009-10. It is India's strong sales that have made her the second fastest growing automobile market after China in the world.

India being one of the world's largest manufacturers of small cars with a strong engineering base and expertise, there are still many segments untapped and un-served those entrepreneurs can focus on in India's automobile and auto components sector in future.

Innovative Automobile Entrepreneurs:

i. EVOMO Research & Advancement - Abhinav Kumar CEO, EVOMO, UP

As a young automobile engineer Abhinav Kumar dreamt of joining a professional racing team. But a casual visit to rural Uttar Pradesh, where he saw a range of locally manufactured vehicles being used to ferry people and goods, changed the 27-year-old's career ambitions.

He realized there was consumer demand for a transport vehicle that was both affordable and reliable. Soon he quit his job and started own venture, Evomo, in 2010. Evomo's rural utility vehicle costs Rs 1.5 lakh, which is less than the price of a Tata Nano, dubbed the world's cheapest car.

ii. Ampere Vehicles – Hemalatha Annamalai, Coimbatore

In Coimbatore, electric-bike maker Ampere Vehicles is selling thousands of bikes being used by retailers to distribute water and milk in villages and they target small entrepreneurs. Founded in 2008 by Hemalatha Annamalai, 45, a computer engineer, the company is expected to reach revenue of Rs 100 crore within the next four years.

3. **Textiles:** India is famous for its textiles since long time. What is worth mentioning that the style of apparel is unique from region to state, thus, offering a diversified market for apparel / textile products in the country? In view of this, India holds good potential to grow as a preferred location for manufacturing textiles taking into account the huge demand for garments.

Places like Tamil Nadu, Tripura and Ludhiana are, for example, now export hubs for textiles in the country. A better understanding of the textiles markets and the varied customer needs can greatly help unleash the potential this sector holds in our country.

4. **Social Ventures:** Like many other developmental activities, entrepreneurship development is also context-specific. The recent social issues providing a different entrepreneurial context has given emergence to yet another breed of entrepreneurship called 'social entrepreneurship'. With a view to ameliorate the social fabric of the society, increasing number of entrepreneurs has started their social ventures.

SEWA and Lizzat Pappad, for example, are such two social ventures hardly get missed while mentioning about social entrepreneurship. Muhammad Yunus's 'Grameen Bank' in Bangladesh is the worldwide known social venture of the recent times.

5. **Engineering Goods:** India continues to be one of the fastest growing exporters of engineering goods, growing at a rate of 30.1 per cent. The government has set a target of \$110 billion by 2014 for total engineering exports. Entrepreneurs must capitalise on the booming demand for products from the engineering industry.

Innovative Entrepreneurs producing Innovative Engineering goods:

1. **Aakar Innovations:** Based out in New Delhi which builds low-cost machines that produce sanitary napkins and which are biodegradable.
2. **nanoPix:** Thirty-six-year-old Sasisekar Krish makes image and video processing products for agriculture and healthcare at his company nanoPix based in Karnataka's Hubli district. Farmers use his product to sort agriculture products like cashew by shape, size, colour and quality. The same technology also helps analyse blood smears to detect infectious diseases. nanoPix has already tied up with a few hospitals in rural Karnataka to use the product. To keep costs low, Krish combines images from several low-cost cameras and uses a software algorithm to create three dimensional models of the objects to be analysed instead of using expensive high-resolution cameras used in imaging technology.
6. **Franchising:** As a boon of New Economic Policy 1991 of the Government of India, now it's well connected with the world economies. Hence, franchising with leading brands to spread across the country could also offer ample opportunities for young entrepreneurs especially in services sector like education and health. With many small towns developing at a fast pace in India, there is vast scope for spreading franchising business in the countryside in future.

Revolutionary Franchising Startup:

- **U S Mahender:** He co-founded HattiKaapi in 2009 to revolutionize the experience of drinking filter coffee by providing **high-quality, authentic and pure filter coffee at affordable prices** to the coffee drinkers of South India. Riding on a stupendous wave of customer satisfaction and business, he has expanded to 16 Hattis across Bangalore including one in Bangalore International Airport(KIA) within a short span of four years. Today, Hattikaapi is known for its consistent long term relationship with the customers, continuous improvement and quality management while keeping reasonable pricing constantly in sight.
7. **Food Processing:** Broadly, food processing industries include cannery, meat packing plant, slaughterhouse, sugar industry, vegetable packing plants, industrial rendering, etc. India's mainstay is agriculture. Entrepreneurs can explore many options in the food-grain cultivation and marketing segments. Inefficient management, lack of infrastructure, proper storage facilities leads to huge losses of food grains and fresh produce in India.

Unfortunately, very small portion of our food production is processed for manufacturing purposes as is evident from the following figures:

<i>Food</i>	<i>Production (million Tonnes)</i>	<i>India's rank in the World</i>	<i>India's Share (%)</i>	<i>India's Share in Exports (%)</i>
Wheat	65	2	12	0.02
Paddy	124	2	22	18
Coarse Grains like maize	29	3	4	-
Milk	98	1	16	Negligible
Fruits	41	2	10	Negligible

Likewise, the level of processing in perishable foods like fruits and vegetables (2.2%), milk and milk products (35%), meat (21%), poultry (6%) and marine products (8%) is also at a quite low level of total production. Thus, it is evident from above figures that there remains a lot of scope for agri-business or agri-preneurship development in the country. As such, small scale entrepreneurs can add value to these produce with proper management and marketing initiatives.

The processed food market opens a great potential for entrepreneurs be it fast food, packaged food or organic food. That there will be more and more demand for readymade or processed food in coming days is already indicated by the meteoritic growth of Mumbai's Dabbawala. Thus, food processing industry offers yet more opportunities for entrepreneurship development to establish and run food-based industries.

- 8. **Ayurveda and Traditional Medicine:** India is well known for its herbal and Ayurvedic products. With increasing awareness about the ill-effects of allopathic medicines, there will be a huge demand for cosmetics, natural medicines and remedies in coming time.
- 9. **Organic Farming:** Organic farming has been in practice in India for long time. That the importance of organic farming will assume increasing importance in the country is evident by the fact that increasing number of consumers especially foreigners have preference towards organic products.

Therefore, the prospective entrepreneurs can focus on business opportunities in this promising sector of the country. Many small-time farmers have already adopted organic farming but the huge demand is still unmet which offers good opportunities for those agri-preneurs who can promote organic farming on a large-scale in the country.

10. **Packaging:** With China invading the markets with cheap plastic goods and packaging materials, there is a good opportunity to develop good packaging materials to meet domestic and foreign demand. There is a huge demand from various sectors like agriculture, automotive, consumer goods, healthcare infrastructure and packaging sectors for plastics.
11. **Floriculture:** India's floriculture segment is small and unorganized. There is a lot to be done in this lucrative sector. The global trade in floriculture products is worth \$9.4 billion. With a 8 per cent growth, it is expected to grow to \$16 billion by 2010. India's share in world trade is just 0.18 per cent. This is a huge market to be tapped considering the rising demand for fresh flowers. More awareness and better farming and infrastructure can boost exports of flowers in coming times.
12. **Recycling Business:** More and more companies are making wealth from waste and, in the process, saving the environment from devastation. And E-waste will rise to alarming proportions in the developing world within a decade, with computer waste in India alone to grow by 500 per cent from 2007 levels by 2020, according to a UN study. Therefore, this sector also opens new vistas of viable business opportunity for entrepreneurs in terms of waste management and disposal activities in large size.

V. CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurship has been on the rise as a global phenomenon much before India began becoming sensitive to the development of entrepreneurship. However the awareness towards the path of entrepreneurship is now picking up a quick pace in our own country, and as a matter of fact is seen as one of the countries that is par excellence with the rest of the Asian countries as far as growing entrepreneurship is concerned. There are ample opportunities in small businesses in India and such opportunities will transform India in the coming future. For such transformation to happen there needs to be support both at the governmental and societal level. For the government it is important to realize that the goal of small business owners will be to remain self-employed.

Such people may not need financial assistance but they will need marketing and legal assistance in order to sustain themselves. Practical and cost effective programs need to be developed to address their needs because self-employed people will represent an important segment in economic revitalization.

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